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THE ROLE OF GENERAL PHYSICAL FITNESS IN INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF GYMNASTIC SPORTS TRAINING IN SCHOOLS

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Abstract: theoretical information about the importance of general physical training in increasing the effectiveness of gymnastics sports clubs in secondary schools is presented.

Key words: sports circles, general physical fitness, motor.

After the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence, great attention was paid to the development of physical culture and sports. Spiritual and educational values, national customs and traditions were restored, especially many activities related to physical education and sports were implemented. Decree No. 5924 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 24, 2020 "On measures to improve and popularize physical education and sports [1] can be cited as a clear proof of this. Sports clubs in general education schools are especially important in the basic preparation of physical education. Sports clubs focus on a certain type of sport, depending on the interest of school students, and help to discover new talents. Taking this into account, it is necessary to study sports clubs of secondary schools in depth.

In general schools, sports clubs are held two or three days a week. In the afternoon, the school's physical education teacher and community guides conduct selected sports. The main purpose of organizing and holding these classes is to improve the health of students and develop their knowledge, skills and physical fitness. In order to achieve the goal of sports club training with young students, first of all, it is necessary for the coach to be able to correctly distribute the load given to the student, because the training conducted with a random load, in children, this gymnastics creates boredom in relation to the sports club. Sports clubs of general education schools are often held on the basis of sports games

(football, volleyball, handball and basketball). Information about the appropriateness of sports clubs for the age of students is given in the literature. According to him, there was information about the possibility of regular participation in these sports clubs from the age of 10-12 and the positive impact of these sports on the physical development and physical fitness of students. Of course, it is very important to attract schoolchildren to sports clubs according to their age, but we cannot achieve the expected result as a result of not taking into account the direction of exercise in the organization of sports clubs. For this reason, we now provide information about the development of physical qualities and physical fitness of students and types of training in sports club training.

It is very important to develop the qualities of the students of the general education school, which they show through their bodies, for the development of physical training in the club training. We talk about these types of physical training and their development in sports circles.

Sports club training is primarily held to improve the health of students, but considering that sports clubs are based on a specific sport, it is possible to achieve results in this sport, even if it is small (school first place, to win competitions between district and regional school students), so that these two goals do not negate each other, we organize this sports club training based on the principle of "the unity of the athlete's general and special physical fitness" We consid-

er it the most reasonable rule when conducting classes [2].

In order to achieve high results, not only the work of the student athlete, but also the role of his coach, school doctor, psychologist, and the created conditions in society is incomparable. Of course, scientific researches in the field of physical culture and sports are very useful for achieving such results in sports, because without the new methods and tools created by them, it would be difficult to achieve such results. Each country uses various means and methods of physical education and sports to make the population of its society healthy and physically fit. Of course, the starting point of this process depends on the correct and appropriate organization of physical education and sports clubs at preschool and school age.

This situation was addressed in the study guide written for students of higher educational institutions whose specialty is not physical culture by Professor Yu. In his definition of health, it is pointed out that high "physical fitness" is not a guarantee of health [3]. It is clear from this that there is a need to organize any training, especially with the proper use of the tools and methods used to educate the young generation through physical education and sports to be healthy and have high physical fitness. In order to achieve this, we believe that it is necessary to know the basic rules appropriate to the tasks and to be based on the principle of the unity of the athlete's general and special training, which is relevant for a correct and effective solution. So, when solving these tasks, we need to study the types of physical training separately for each of them.

General physical training is understood as a long-term pedagogical process aimed at developing the movement qualities of the human body equally, not one above the other, but developing all of them (comprehensive physical training).

Today, the basis of the physical culture of a healthy lifestyle, which has risen to the

level of state policy, is to solve the issue of improving the general physical fitness of a member of society. The content, tools, methods and activities of this training are aimed at creating comprehensive basic physical training in all forms of student activity, whether it is in the form of sports activities or labor process activities.

In the process of general physical training, the following tasks are mainly solved, they are:

a) by influencing the comprehensive physical development of the students' organism, by educating the qualities of endurance, strength, quickness, agility and flexibility, creating a favorable environment for students to maintain the level of movement activity appropriate for their age, not only in class activities, but also during their future work activities;

b) strengthening the health of the participants of the circle, strengthening the ability of the body to resist the harmful factors of the external environment;

d) creating conditions for active rest and recovery of the body in cases of reduced working capacity during study and training;

e) gives a very positive result for strengthening the willpower to overcome additional or unexpected difficulties in training and solving other life tasks [4]. Of course, a tool is needed to solve such tasks in sports club training.

Means of general physical training - exercises on gymnastic equipment, general development performed with and without bodies, exercises of sports or their elements and other weight lifting, exercises performed with one's own body weight and overcoming external resistance are used. Exercises that ensure the active functioning of all our organs and systems (walking, running, walks, trips) play an important role in general physical fitness. Using them to increase the level of service and capabilities of our members, organs and systems that are lagging behind in their training and development, and whose functional status is not good will be the same. If the aforemen-

tioned tools are combined with the health-giving forces of nature in sports training, the goal expected from the effectiveness of the physical training process will be achieved quickly and easily.

From general physical training to all stages of physical education, more is carried out in the school physical education system, through mass physical culture events, work, and various forms of individual training with physical exercises. The content of such classes is aimed at improving the health of students and comprehensively developing movement qualities. However, as we mentioned above, sports club classes are organized by any type of sport, and this process requires students to compete. In the process of competition, it will be difficult for children with high general physical fitness but weak special physical fitness to win. For this reason, we have provided information on how to perform special physical training in sports club training.

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